

The Metaproteomics Initiative's Organizational Structure

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Mission and Vision

We promote dissemination of metaproteomics fundamentals, advancements, and applications through collaborative networking in microbiome research. We aim to be the central information hub and open meeting place where newcomers and experts interact to communicate, standardize and accelerate experimental and bioinformatic methodologies in this field.

Organizational chart

This organizational chart represents the structure of the Initiative. However, as time goes by, this structure can be evaluated and improved.

The Executive Board

The Executive Board (EB) is composed of active members responsible for the tasks required for the proper day-to-day functioning of the Metaproteomics Initiative. The EB consists of the following roles: Administrator (2), Secretary (1), Communication (1), Webmaster (1), Education (1), Early Career Representatives (2), Scientific Advisors (6), Symposium Organizers, and International Correspondence (1 per continent not yet represented). The EB meetings are held regularly and discuss the logistics, administration, and projects of the Initiative. These meetings are intended for the elected EB members, but non-elected interested members may join on request. Only EB members have the ability to vote and make decisions.

The EB consists of the following roles:

- Administrator (2)
 - Tasks: lead and prepare meetings and agenda, responsible for budget reports, keep contact with other organizations such as EuPA and HUPO.
- Secretary (1)
 - Tasks: taking notes during meetings, listing to-do's
- Communication (1)
 - Tasks: prepares the newsletter and X, BlueSky and LinkedIn, reach out to researchers from closely related fields (e.g. biology, microbiology, microbiome research, bioinformatics, statistics,...) and introduce the Initiative, prepare promotional material
- Webmaster (1)
 - Task: take care of the website (experience with GitHub is preferred) and Slack.
- Early Career Representatives (1)
 - Tasks: organize events for ECR members, reach out to ECR initiatives from EuPA/HUPO
- Scientific Advisors (6)
 - Task: provide scientific advice and a longer term vision to the Initiative, notably regarding the Working Groups and community projects. These advisors must be experts in ideally different fields (e.g. sample processing, bioinformatics, multi-omics). The scientific advisors form together the Scientific Committee. Within the Scientific Committee, one member acts as coordinator of the Working Groups.
- Symposium organizers (incoming and outgoing)
 - Tasks: organize the International Metaproteomics Symposium, and provide advice to the new organizer afterwards
- Education (1)
 - Tasks: reach out to new researchers via educational material, and collect and list educational material on the website.

The EB meetings will be organized regularly and will discuss the logistics and administration of running the Initiative, but not include scientific discussions. Between the meetings, the EB members can contact each other via a designated *Slack channel*. In first place, these meetings are intended for the elected EB members, but non-elected, interested members can join on request (info@metaproteomics.org).

Working Groups

Definition and examples

Next to the EB, there will be Working Groups (WG). A WG is defined as a group of researchers with a clearly defined task that aligns with the Initiative's Mission and Vision statement. This task has a clearly defined, realistic end goal, and once this goal has been reached, the WG will be closed.

A few examples of potential WGs:

- "CAMPI x - multi-lab comparison of sample processing techniques"
 - Goal: manuscript about comparison of commonly used sample processing techniques in metaproteomics
→ This WG will be closed once the manuscript is published.
- "Summer school 202x"
 - Goal: Organize a summer school about metaproteomics in the summer of 202x
→ This WG will be closed once the summer school has finished.
- "Sample processing techniques"
 - Goal: discussing sample processing techniques
→ This is **not** a valid WG, there's no clear end goal. We should avoid these.
 - Goal: "Develop a tutorial describing the sample processing protocols used in CAMPI"
→ This, however, is a valid WG. The WG will be closed when the tutorial is finished.

Initiating a WG

New WGs should be presented at an EB meeting so that members are informed and can provide input where relevant.

Members

Everyone can freely join the Initiative by filling in [the registration form](#). In addition, if labs want their name listed on our website, they can fill in [this lab registration form](#). After registration, members receive an invite to [Slack](#), where they can interact with each other. They can ask here for scientific advice, post proposals for new WGs or request to join existing WGs.

Election Procedure

The elections for the EB of the Metaproteomics Initiative take place online. An online voting system is set up to allow all members to vote. Candidates must be members of the Metaproteomics Initiative, and declare their candidacy by filling out a form provided by the current EB. The mandate length is three years, and EB members can serve a maximum of two consecutive terms, regardless of their position in the EB (a total of six years). After

completing two consecutive terms, an EB member cannot re-apply for a minimum period of one election cycle of three years.

In the event that not all positions are filled during an election, EB members who have completed their maximum term may re-apply for vacant positions.

In addition, it's important to note that the main symposium organizers, although an integral part of the EB, are not subject to direct elections. The main organizers of the previous and next symposium will be automatically included in the EB, and can put themselves (additionally) forward as candidates for another position.

Furthermore, scientific advisors provide a long-term vision to the Initiative, and are therefore directly elected for the maximum of two consecutive terms (six years). After the elections, the outgoing and newly elected boards overlap for a reasonable transition time to ensure continuity of the work, as agreed by the outgoing and incoming EB.

Additionally, candidates have the option to apply for multiple positions, prioritizing their preferences. If a candidate is not elected for their first priority position, they retain eligibility for their subsequent preferences. Furthermore, the EB possesses the authority to co-opt any positions that remain unfilled post-election, ensuring the effective functioning of the EB and the fulfillment of its responsibilities.

The Election Procedure of the Metaproteomics Initiative is subject to amendment by a two-thirds majority vote of the members, based on the votes cast. This vote will take place online to ensure all members can participate. If the amendments are approved, they will take effect immediately.